

THE ISSUE OF MODELING THE TEACHER'S ACTIVITY IN THE EDUCATION OF THE MOTHER TONGUE OF THE PRIMARY GRADE.

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Annotation: In this article, the issue of modeling teacher's activity in primary grade mother tongue education is scientifically and theoretically analyzed.

Key words: Education, State Education Standards, Korea, England, level of knowledge, history, natural sciences, literature, elementary school, question-answer, accuracy, correctness, etc.

The teacher manages and controls the process of assimilation of educational content by students, and determines the level of achievement of educational goals. The educational goal, the educational and methodological tasks necessary to achieve the educational goal, how to control the stages between the achievement of the goal and the overall results, what aids to use, what information to collect about the learner It defines the elements that are important for education, such as what methods of teaching should be used, what are the evaluation criteria of the learner. It is known that the main attitude in the educational process is the teacher. and the relationship between the student. In creative education, this connection takes the main place, changing its form. Links in traditional education include teacher and textbook, teacher and learning material, teacher and visual aids, learner and textbook, learner and learning material, o If such things as a student and a visual aid are included, their form changes somewhat in computer-based education. From the point of view of the

teacher who works in order to design the creative activity of students in mother tongue education, teacher and textbook, teacher and learning material, teacher and visual aids connections, ready From the perspective of a teacher teaching using a project, teacher and project, teacher and student, student and student connections, and student and learning material connections apply. . First, let's talk about the activity of the teacher involved in the design. Naturally, the effectiveness of education depends on the quality of the created project. two levels of activity are observed in the structure of design activity: the creative character of design, which involves the creation of new knowledge in the form of a project; the individual character of design, which reflects the personality of a pedagogue in a project created based on the study of the experience of advanced pedagogues. It is necessary to consider the design activity as a part of the pedagogue's professional competence, which represents the unity of theoretical and practical preparation for the implementation of pedagogical activities and describes the professional quality. Theoretical preparation for design activities is a high level of mastery of the set of design skills and competencies. Diagnosing G.Ye.Muraveva's design skills as predicting the outcome of the development of the didactic process; project implementation planning; construction of the technological process for the creation of material means; introduces modeling issues of obtaining new information about an object. A. Slastenin is a set of competencies that determine the teacher's theoretical preparation for design activity, reflexive that provides self-improvement of pedagogical activity; cognitive, which develops the ability to increase its methodical level; skills and competencies related to obtaining information and its applicationformative educational; communicative, which develops the technology of oral and written communication; introduces social competence, which leads to the understanding of the essence of his professional competence. Designing the goal of education, which is considered the leader in pedagogical technology, remains one of the most important problems in the design of education. They can be expressed

as follows: when studying educational subjects, first of all, determining the level of learning basic concepts and designing their learning;

- * designing the relevance of the basic concepts to educational standards, educational programs, and the student's future activities;

- * designing teaching methods; designing the student's level of preparation;

- * ensuring consistency of teaching content with the set goal;

- * pre-planning of educational methods, which of them should be used at which stage of the lesson;

- * designing the level of acquisition of knowledge and skills by students in different types of lessons;

- * designing the use of various methods of control and verification in the teaching process;

- * design effective use of modern information in each lesson;

- * advance recording of the ways, means, and results to be achieved in the preparation of educational material texts;

- * creating a base of goals and tasks for the educational subject, designing its completion through assessment, etc.

The process of teaching new material is organized based on the characteristics of the educational material. If the theoretical material is not large in terms of volume, it is better to teach it in parts and move on to strengthening it. If the learning material is large in size and it is possible to divide it into interconnected parts, it is useful to explain it by parts. Teaching the educational material by dividing it into logically connected parts leads to a conscious feeling of the structure of the acquired knowledge as much as possible, to mentally imagine the connection of this knowledge with the previously learned knowledge. All this is solved by the teacher in the process of pedagogical processing of the educational material. As President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev stated, the important task in this regard is "related to the quality of education in general education schools, lyceums and vocational colleges, as well

as higher educational institutions". The main task of the education system today is to bring up a mature generation who has mastered knowledge, skills and abilities and is able to occupy a worthy place in society. The rapid development of science, technology and production requires raising the quality of education in all educational institutions to a new level in terms of content. This, in turn, imposes responsible tasks on teachers. Competency education is not only the acquisition of a certain set of knowledge, but also the development of personality., forms the ability to understand and create. For this reason, basic competences related to all subjects and competences related to each subject are given. In particular, there are speech and linguistic competences related to the subject of the mother tongue, which are of particular importance. The main task of teaching the science of the mother tongue is to develop speech competence aimed at making students think, understand the opinions of others, to be able to express their own opinion in oral and written form, to acquire knowledge of grammar (phonetics) in students. , lexicology, word structure, word formation, morphology, syntax, writing and spelling, punctuation, speech styles, stylistic concepts) and formation of linguistic competences using the broad possibilities of the mother tongue.

In speech competence, listening comprehension, reading, speaking, and writing are developed, while in linguistic competence, concepts related to phonetics, syntax, lexicology, morphology, and punctuation are developed. The development of speech and linguistic competences in the study of the syntax and punctuation sections of linguistics given in the textbook of the native language of the class will be in the following order.

Pupils in speech competence:

- * can understand the text listened to, exercises and tasks or dictation;
- * can read exercises and tasks related to the topic, following the rules of orthography;
- * can express his opinion correctly, can put the accent correctly;

* can write vocabulary, selective, emphatic dictations and control dictation consisting of 85-95 words within the studied topics;

* Courtesy and spelling follow the rules;

* can create a creative text of 8-10 sentences;

* can think independently and creatively.

Students in linguistic competence:

* learns new words and phrases.

* can distinguish and interpret the connection of words in a sentence, word combinations, types of sentences according to the purpose of expression, clauses, prepositions, prepositions, simple and compound sentences, quotations and dialogues ;

* can analyze words morphologically;

* correctly uses learned means of expression in oral and written speech.

Mother tongue training is seen in the basis of stepwise sequence, relationship of form and content, and close interrelationship of linguistic departments.

Therefore, the first quarter of the 5th grade is devoted to mastering the necessary concepts of syntax - simple and compound sentences, the center of a sentence, clauses, adverbial and compound clauses, abstract sentences, punctuation marks in them. At the beginning of the second quarter, students are introduced to the important concepts of lexicology and morphology: the meaning of a word, its own meaning and figurative meaning, synonyms, nested words, antonyms. Basic information about nouns, adverbs, root words, independent and auxiliary word groups, stem, suffix, form-forming and word-forming adverbs is given. .We are making it easier for 5th graders to learn linguistics, and we are showing the importance of comparison in explaining topics. As we know, there are several possibilities in the mother tongue to explain the topic and express the idea. They can be conveyed to the reader through pictures and media resources of various forms and appearances. It will be more memorable and understandable if we compare it to

a tree, its branches and leaves, and compare it to the "Family Tree" in order to develop linguistic competence and to explain the sections of linguistics in a simpler way. The 5th grade native language textbook contains information on the correct spelling of words, spelling rules, places of use of punctuation marks, lexicology (the science of words), lexicology, etc.

References.

Hayitov H. A. Sharq mumtoz adabiyotida ohang talqini //Мировая наука. – 2019. – №. 8. – С. 3-5.

Hayitov H. A. Literary influence and artistic image //Экономика и социум. – 2019. – №. 8. – С. 11-14.

Ahmadovich H. H., Amrullojeva S. D. XX ASR QISSACHILIGI TARAQQIYOTIDA FOLKLORNING LATIFA JANRI TA'SIRI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 302-304.

Ahmadovich H. H. Expression of Folklorisms in the Works of Ghafur Ghulam //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – 2022. – T. 14. – С. 101-105.

Ahmadovich H. H. et al. BOSHLANG 'ICH SINFLARDA O 'ZBEK QISSALARI TAHLILINING INNOVATSION USULLARI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 350-352.

Ahmadovich H. H. et al. O 'RXUN-YENISEY BITIKLARIDA TALIM-TARBIYA TO 'G 'RISIDAGI FIKRLARNING YORITILISHI VA ULARNING TARBIYAVIY AHAMIYATI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 349-350.

Ahmadovich H. H. et al. IJODIY TOPSHIRIQLAR O 'QUV MOTIVLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING SAMARALI VOSITASI SIFATIDA //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 293-294.

Ahmadovich H. H. et al. BOSHLANG ‘ICH TA’LIMDA O ‘ZLASHTIRISH JARAYONINING PSIXO-DIDAKTIK ASOSLARI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 332-334.

Ahmadovich H. H. et al. O ‘QUVCHILARNING BILUV FAOLLIGINI OSHIRISHGA QARATILGAN DARSDAN TASHQARI ISHLAR VA ULARNI TASHKIL ETISH METODIKASI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 343-345.

Ahtamovich H. H., Shixnazarovna J. A. O ‘QUVCHILAR O ‘ZLASHTIRISH DARAJALARINI TASHHISLASH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 306-309.

Ahmadovich H. H., Aminovna A. S. BOSHLANG ‘ICH SINFI O ‘QISH DARSLARIDA DIDAKTIK O ‘YIN VA INTERFAOL USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 100-102.

Ahmadovich H. H., Amrulloevna S. D. RUNN BITIKLARI AXLOQ VA VATANPARVARLIKNING YUKSAK NAMUNASI SIFATIDA //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 248-250.

Ahmadovich K. H., Bahridinovna S. G. Development and practical application of acmeological technologies of student assessment diagnose //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 6. – C. 141-145.

Ahmadovich K. H., Zokirovna Z. A. G. THE PROBLEM OF HUMAN EDUCATION AND MORALITY IN FOLKLORE //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – T. 25. – C. 133-137.

Ahmadovich K. H., Nodirkulovna A. I. Theory of Fairy Tales in Primary Grades, The Nature of the Fairy Tale Genre //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 7. – C. 130-133.

BuxDUPI H. A. H. et al. AKMEOLOGIYA VA UNING O’QUVCHILAR O’ZLASHTIRISHINI TASHXISLASHDAGI O’RNI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 415-417.

Хайтов Х. Адабиётда кулгидан фойдаланиш анъанасининг асослари //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3/S. – С. 49-52.

Ҳайитов Ҳ. А. ЛЎЛИ НОМИ БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ ЛАТИФАЛАРНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //Интернаука. – 2021. – №. 17-4. – С. 51-52.

Hayitov H. A. QUSHLARGA IBRAT-HAZRATI XIZR! //Интернаука. – 2020. – №. 12-3. – С. 72-73.

Khoja o'g'li T., Ahmadovich K. H. Advanced Characteristics of the Tradition of Using Uzbek Folk Humor Art in Written Literature //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 9. – С. 1-4.

Khaitov H., Amonova S. ЎЗБЕК ҲИКОЯ ВА ҚИССАЛАРИДА КУЛГИ МАДАНИЯТИНИНГ ИЛДИЗЛАРИ //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 140-144.

Ahtamovich H. H., Shixnazarovna J. A. О ‘QUVCHILAR О ‘ZLASHTIRISH DARAJALARINI TASHHISLASH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 306-309.

Ahmadovich X. X. et al. ENG QADIMGI MA'RIFIY YODGORLIKLARNI O 'RGANISHNING AHAMIYATI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 281-285.

Ҳайитов Х. А. ҒАФУР ҒУЛОМНИНГ ХАЛҚ ЛАТИФАЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ МАҲОРАТИ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 679-687.

Akhmadovich H. H. Khoja nasriddin afandi as people's hero //ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 2. – С. 1562-1565.

Akhmadovich K. K. Symbolism of Birds in Uzbek Literature //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 59-63.